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The Role of VET on the Inclusion of Marginalized Young People and Adult People from a Lifelong Perspective across the Lifespan

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Abstract

In the current changing social, educational and labour contexts –where the transitions of marginalized young people and adult people from education into work and into adult life have become a difficult process– VET can develop a crucial role. Within a lifelong perspective across the lifespan, this work explores two areas around the role of VET where the perspective of inclusion in education and in the labour market as well as in adult social life can provide better knowledge in order to improve the quality of VET practices and policies. On the one hand, VET –in particular basic and/or initial VET– and on the other one, work based learning –in particular of VET perspective focused on how the social economy motto of putting people before profits is applied to the vocational qualification processes– are examples of ways in order to help young and adult marginalized people in their inclusion and hence contributing to citizenship.

Keywords

vocational education and training; inclusion; marginalized groups; lifelong learning; precariousness

Introduction

In September 2015 the UN published 17 sustainability goals that are designed to “end poverty, protect the planet and ensure prosperity for all” by 2030. Goal 4 focuses on education and calls for an ‘inclusive and quality’ provision for all.

VET can develop a crucial role on the achievement of this goal from a lifelong perspective across the lifespan, especially on the transitions from education into work and into adult work, in the current changing social, educational and labour contexts where such transitions have become a difficult process. This proposal explores two areas around VET role where the perspective of inclusion in education and in the labour market can provide better knowledge in order to improve the quality of VET practices and policies.

The first area is that of marginalized young people facing difficult transitions due to factors of vulnerability such as disability, unskilled profiles, or early school leaving situations, to name only a few. Normally, the lack of these personal resources and skills is one of the main reasons linked to their risk of being excluded (Schwartz, Côté & Jensen, 2005; Tagliabue et al., 2016; Thompson, Russell & Simmons, 2014). Against this background, education and training are considered key factors for providing young people with all those resources and skills that are required to cope with the demands of functioning effectively in these meaningful social, educational and labour contexts. VET –in particular basic and/or initial VET– is perceived as a strategic pathway, and alternative itinerary for tackling disadvantaged situation and improving

young people's opportunities for participating, hence contributing to their inclusion (CEDEFOP, 2016; European Commission, 2011; OECD, 2014; Olmos-Rueda & Mas-Torelló, 2013, Abiétar-López et al., 2017).

The second area deals with the inclusion of marginalized adult people through work based learning among others (accreditation of prior learning, access to VET, access to further education after completion of VET). Based upon two research projects³ conducted since 2007 in Spain (Marhuenda et al., 2010; Córdoba & Martínez, 2011; Chisvert et al., 2015; Marhuenda, 2016), VET perspective is focused on how the social economy motto of putting people before profits is applied to the vocational qualification processes of adults who have suffered long-term unemployment, single parents or migrant people, whose difficulties in adult life can be addressed through work and qualification in the vocational as well as in the personal and social domains, in order to help them out of poverty and social exclusion and hence contributing to citizenship (Marhuenda, 2017).

VET and marginalized young people's inclusion

Young people's inclusion in the current changing social, educational and labour contexts becomes a difficult process especially for all those young people facing difficult transitions due to factors related to vulnerable situations such as disability, unskilled profiles, early school leaving situations, to name only a few. Normally, the lack of these young people's personal resources and skills is one of the main argued reasons linked to their risk of being excluded from these (Schwartz, Côté, & Jensen, 2005; Tagliabue et al., 2016; Thompson, Russell, & Simmons, 2014). This mistrust is worse for disabled young people –especially for intellectual disabled young people– due to common misconception of the society and the workforce about their strengths, capacities and competencies for coping with the skills and levels of qualification and mediating concepts that are required by social, educational and labour contexts –see, for example, initiative, self-reliance, or adaptability, to name a few–. Regarding this misconception of disability, it is worth catching here the conception of disability of authors such as Hahn (1986, p. 128) or Oliver (1990, p. xiv), who state that disability emerges from the failure of a structured social setting when it has to adjust to disadvantaged citizens' needs and aspirations, rather than individuals' inability to adapt themselves to the demands of society.

Against this background, education and training –understood in terms of lifelong learning (LLL)– are considered key factors for providing young people with all those resources and skills that are required to cope with the demands of functioning effectively in these meaningful social, educational and labour contexts. VET –in particular basic and initial VET– is perceived as a strategic pathway, and alternative itinerary for tackling these young people's disadvantaged and vulnerable situation, and improving their opportunities for participating in these contexts, helping to their inclusion and social transformation. In other words, basic VET contribute to these young people's transitions, and support these vulnerable young people to become active citizens (Abiétar-López, Marhuenda-Fluixá, & Navas-Saurin, 2017; CEDEFOP, 2016; OECD, 2014; Olmos, 2013; Olmos-Rueda, 2017).

As it said before, through basic VET –and its respective programmes– young people can acquire basic skills and/or competencies that are key to getting their personal and social development and achieving educational and labour outcomes (CEDEFOP, 2011), and where educational and work agents play an important role. Tutors –as educational agents– and entrepreneurs –as work agents– have to work together, and with these youths, in the development of instrumental competencies –communicative, mathematical and digital competencies–, social and civic competencies, capacity of autonomy and initiative, learning to learn, emotional health –intrapersonal intelligence–, self-esteem, resilience, responsibility, punctuality, capacity for team working, or taking decisions, to give some of the most significant examples of basic VET

³ EDU2013-45919-R and SEJ2007-62145/EDUC

programmes provision addressed to vulnerable young people in terms of social, educational and labour inclusion (Olmos-Rueda & Mas-Torelló, 2017).

Basic VET programmes aim to work these basic skills and/or competencies, which are crucial for the improvement of young people's employability. Therefore, it is worth saying basic VET programmes –understood as a second chance to these youths at risk of exclusion that provide them with the opportunity of an educational and labour reintegration– have a positive impact on most of them, who get the educational support needed to achieve the education enabling them to be an acknowledged and productive members of society. However, according to some basic VET researches (Amores & Ritacco, 2016; Cedefop, 2016; Martínez-Carmona, Gil del Pino, & Álvarez-Castillo, 2016; Olmos & Mas, 2013; Mas, Olmos, & Salvà, 2017), some improvements are needed by these basic VET programmes. These improvements are linked to the adaptation of the strategies that are used for attending these young people's diversity – especially young people with disability, who are under-represented in basic VET programmes that do not have an adequate training offering, making difficult their access to the job market (Dincat, 2015)–, the improvement of teachers' pedagogical profile, the work for better young people's guidance processes in order to support their transitions, or the work with the families, the community, and other social, educational and work agents.

In the light of these results and reflections, it is needed to continue working on VET pathways for making these a really alternative for the educational, social and labour inclusion of this vulnerable group, all those young people who facing difficult transitions due to factors that are mainly related to unskilled profiles, and usually are linked to disabled condition and early school leaving situations.

Can VET play a role in the successful inclusion of adult people at risk of social exclusion?

For more than half a century in Western Europe, employment relations have been at the core of adult life. Being an adult consisted in having employment, being occupied, working for an employer or running your own business. Adulthood was related to your position in the world of work, submitted to its hierarchies, related to the wages related to those positions. Such positions were understood as the fruit of one's education, under the assumption that an specialized occupational or professional education (vocational education and training) would bring you to a certain position in society, based upon merit and professional accredited knowledge.

The agreement between capital and work, employers and employees, was the basis for the welfare state that Europe experienced between the end of the II World War and the turn of the century. Such agreement and relation, as the ILO (2016) has shown, has shifted towards an increase of what has been named 'non-standard forms of employment', 'precariousness' (Standing, 2011), or 'the working poor' (Shipler, 2005), to name a few. Employment relations have become loose and flexible, the labour market has experienced increased deregulation in some European countries (Cosubiela & Rojo, 2012), and the nature and role of work is changing in a large scale.

Vocational education and training was developed and built under the industrial idea of work and the employment relations where qualification played a relevant role, and if those notions are being questioned nowadays, there is good ground for calling a conference like SFIVET has done, 'the end of VET as we know it?'⁴. Can we conceive of vocational education without safe and long-term employment relations? Can we think of VET without a career perspective, where one's qualification are increased and evolve along the lifespan? Can we think of VET when unemployment rates are very high (Sanchis, 2016) or in relation to minijobs? If the panorama of work and its development is changing into unknown directions, does it still keep all of its

⁴ 6th Congress on Research on Vocational Education and Training in Switzerland, <https://www.sfivet.swiss/vet-congress-2019>

different values (Budd, 2014) and meanings along recent history (Díez, 2014); or do we have to start thinking of its devastation (Ovejero, 2014)?

The relevance of these questions is much greater if we think them in relation to adult people who are at risk of social exclusion for not being able to join the labour market and therefore being kept away from most of the ordinary relations in adult life. Among these, we can find unemployed adults, adult people with disabilities, adult people with mental health illnesses, adult people after long periods of addictions or of imprisonment, migrant adults whose qualifications and skills are not recognized.

For most companies, these people are seen as part of a disposable workforce and there is mistrust against them in recruiting practices, as well as considerably less options for upskilling offers and VET of any kind. They are often considered mainly a subject of social policy rather than of labour policy, and it is often the case that active employment policies addressed to these populations play more of a social role than a qualifying one.

However, the social economy (Monzón & Chaves, 2017) is able to put the person before the profit and to give work a social value, not just an instrumental one, by which employees show their skills and knowledge, contribute to production processes and the benefits are not just individual but also regional, in terms of social development.

The social economy shows that investing in people provides returns to the companies, and considers VET as part of that investment, and there are several examples of these around Spain ([Faedei](#), [Gureak](#), [Lantegi Batuak](#), [Proyecto Trèvol](#), [Aeress](#) or the [Asociación Española de Escuelas de Segunda Oportunidad](#)). In most of them, there are examples of intersection of VET with special education, intercultural education and adult education. In several of them there is preparation for work and for employment and citizenship, practices to increase the employability and sometimes even entrepreneurship, but with a clear purpose on the inclusion of adult people who have suffered in their lives back into the labour market as independent citizens.

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Minutes

The role of VET and social inclusion was the fourth and last impetus presentation to the research community participating in the meeting. This allowed us presenters to realize that the previous three presentations had addressed already questions relevant to social inclusion, as follows:

1. Societal eco-systems:
 - Stakeholders and VET providers establish a bidirectional relation, it is not just that VET providers have to be responsive to the needs of the labour market, the labour market can be inclusive and incorporate well trained and educated people no matter what record of past exclusion of vulnerability
 - If inclusion is a goal, it has to be a common one, shared by employers in order to make it effective. If inclusion is not a goal for them, they will not cooperate and efforts made by VET providers will be useless
 - Trust between sectors and actors may also foster the will to facilitate social inclusion, giving trainees a chance to show their abilities
 - Transition between life phases, stages and spheres is harder for those in need of support for social inclusion, but it is their right to, if they have been able to accomplish a VET qualification, which gives proof of their skills
 - Lifelong learning is today an obligation behind other notions like second chance or fostering employability
 - A prospective approach to vocational guidance should take into account social inclusion

2. Apprenticeship reform:
 - Freedom to choose your professional pathway demands conditions to make it available, and this is at stake for people at risk of social exclusion
 - Insofar apprenticeships entail the features of ordinary precarious employment, so they might be a good preparation for the current working chances and conditions, is this the kind of vocational preparation we are looking for?
 - Social inclusion after VET is not only a matter for large companies, but also for small and medium ones; and this demands support measures
 - Social responsibility in apprenticeships is necessary for the recognition of qualifications is expected, not just a market-driven preparation for a job; qualifications demand standardization and decent working and learning conditions
 - The liberalization of VET and apprenticeships in several countries has not proved inclusive

3. VET cycle:
 - The prospect of a career from apprentice to manager is appealing in terms of social inclusion, for it allows people to follow their expectations of progress
 - Access to further education along the lifespan is key to assure inclusion not only at

- work but also in terms of increasing one's qualification
- Trainers in apprenticeship schemes need training themselves, also in terms of promoting inclusion practices in the apprenticeships
- The emphasis on transversal skills favours social inclusion, as most of these skills are relevant not only for work but also for life purposes
- Social inclusion approaches warn us about too narrow approaches to VET at the lowest levels of qualification, encouraging people to upskill and promote in terms of a career instead of just finding a job
- Work based learning has long been considered a facilitator of social inclusion, for it provides a different approach to traditional academic learning

To add on these, we summarize here the main topics raised and discussed along the session:

- Focusing on marginalized groups runs the risk of stereotyping marginalization, and this should be avoided
- Skills monitoring and career guidance would help school to work transition for people at risk
- Entrepreneurship education in VET to reduce the risks of disadvantaged youth has not proved a successful alternative in the past. However, entrepreneurship as a competence is a goal that is valuable for all, not being limited to setting up own business
- Flexibility in training provision is a key to facilitate social inclusion, universal design of courses let learners approach their learning at a pace that recognises their different learning needs
- Broad vocational profiles, transversal skills and work process learning approaches facilitate a broad and inclusive career perspective
- Personalization of training and pathways by teachers and trainers suits the needs of people with disabilities, with a 'no-one-size-fits-all' approach; even if it has a higher cost it is conducive to higher quality and effectiveness for all
- New technologies should be used to facilitate learning to people with special needs
- The current context of increasing precarious pathways, zero-hour contracts, crowd-sourcing ... endangers people
- A focus on transversal skills and intrapersonal skills should be highlighted in curriculum design
- Good practices and data from them should be used to persuade employers to introduce inclusion in their policies, we should make visible those successful experiences
- Inclusive systems are often internally exclusive; is it possible to have a VET system inclusive when it is preparing for a selective labour market?
- We must address the confrontation between high quality and high inclusion
- Learning to learn is at the core of a perspective of social inclusion, with a focus upon transversal skills
- Cooperation with employers is necessary if social inclusion after VET is a goal
- Is VET the best educational chance to assure inclusion of marginalized young people? The working logic is not precisely inclusive
- Is VET able to cope with social policy as well as with economic promotion? Are both compatible?
- Inclusion (social, educational, work inclusion) is a condition of quality. To talk about VET quality and quality VET pathways requires taking into consideration the need of working on marginalized (vulnerable) young people's inclusion. It is key a definition of quality compatible with inclusion.

Report on the VETNET research workshop
during the third EU Vocational Skills Week in Vienna, 07.11.2018

Vocational education and training across the lifespan

Christof Nägele, Michael Gessler, Barbara E. Stalder (Editors)

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Introduction

VETNET mission

The Vocational Education and Training Network VETNET is an open network, which welcomes contributions from all over the world as long as they are in line with the goals of VETNET.

VETNET is focusing on research and development in the field of initial, higher and continuing vocational education and training (VET) and learning across the life-span.

The goals of VETNET are to promote research on vocational education and training and to contribute its development by:

- fostering a high quality of research in the field of vocational education and training;
- exploring the relationship between research, policy and practice;
- stimulating the multidisciplinary discussion and dissemination of research results in the European research area and beyond through mutual learning;
- encouraging, establishing and maintaining cooperation between VET researchers and project partnerships in the European research area through, e.g., organising the VETNET programme at the ECER, Crossing Boundaries or Stockhol International Conference; developing international contacts; cooperating with other relevant conferences; publications or by producing electronic or other newsletters;
- maintaining the peer-reviewed VETNET journal IJRNET, the VETNET ECER proceedings and contributing to other international publications; maintaining the community website vetnetsite.org.

VETNET

- maintains a community website on vetnetsite.org;
- has an entry on the EERA website: <https://eera-ecer.de/networks/2-vocational-education-and-training-vetnet/>;
- has a project on [researchgate.net](https://www.researchgate.net/project/IRNVET-VETNET-International-Research-Network-in-Vocational-Education-and-Training-VETNET-European-Research-Network-in-Vocational-Education-and-Training): <https://www.researchgate.net/project/IRNVET-VETNET-International-Research-Network-in-Vocational-Education-and-Training-VETNET-European-Research-Network-in-Vocational-Education-and-Training>;
- has a community on <https://zenodo.org/communities/vetnet/> to host the conference proceedings.

Aim and scope of the workshop

The topic of the researchers' workshop at the EU Vocational Skills Week 2018 in Vienna was: "Vocational education and training across the lifespan".

All participants contributed to the workshop with a short abstract on the topic "Vocational education and training across the lifespan" and a short bibliography.

Four presentations were selected as impetus presentations. These were short presentations by the authors to stimulate the discussion in the workshop. After the discussion, the presenters of the impetus presentations wrote short minutes on the discussion during the workshop. The impetus presentations and minutes are covered in this report.

Programme of the workshop

Introduction

- Dr Christof Nägele
Senior Researcher, University of Applied Sciences and Arts, Northwestern Switzerland
- Dr Dr h.c. Michael Gessler
Professor, Institute Technology and Education, University of Bremen
- Mantas Sekmokas
Policy Officer, European Commission, DG Employment, Social Affairs and Inclusion

Impetus Presentations

Lifelong learning and VET: towards understanding the influence of societal eco-systems on learning across the lifespan

- Dr Natalia (Natasha) Kersh
UCL Institute of Education, University of London
- Dr Karen Evans
Professor Emeritus, UCL Institute of Education, University of London

Apprenticeship Reform in France

- Eric Dumartin
Vice-President of Fongecif Île-de-France, Vice-President of IAE Paris I Panthéon Sorbonne

The VET Skills Cycle and the Formation of Construction Management Skills in Ireland

- Eoghan Ó Murchadha
Assistant Head of Department of Craft, Design, Construction and Apprenticeship, Dún Laoghaire Further Education Institute in Dublin

The Role of VET on the Inclusion of Marginalized Young People and Adult People from a Lifelong Perspective across the Lifespan

- Dr Patricia Olmos Rueda
Professor, Autonomous University of Barcelona (UAB)
- Dr Fernando Marhuenda
Professor, University of Valencia

Outlook

- Dr Dr h.c. Michael Gessler & Dr Christof Nägele